

Rhabdomyolysis In Critically Ill Patients In ICU; Diagnosis And Management

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Rhabdomyolysis is a multifactorial and multicausal syndrome that results in electrolyte disturbances and rise of sarcolemmal proteins in body fluids. It presents variably from asymptomatic elevation of creatine kinase (CK) and myoglobin in blood to a life-threatening fulminant acute kidney injury (AKI).

Aim of the study: To determine the level of CK that is associated with significant renal dysfunction and other complications among polytraumatized patients.

Patients & methods: Our study was a prospective cross-sectional descriptive study conducted on 50 patients admitted to I.C.U at Al-Helal trauma Centre and Kasr Al-Aini University hospital during the period from October 2015 to August 2016; all the studied populations were diagnosed to have multiple traumas (ISS \geq 16) and had duration of stay 3 days at least. Patients known to have chronic kidney disease were excluded.

Results: Among our patient population 32 patient (64%) were diagnosed with rhabdomyolysis. Twenty four percent of our patients developed AKI according to RIFLE criteria. All patients (100%) who developed AKI had rhabdomyolysis, and (41.7%) of them were in risk stage, (8.3%) were in the injury stage and (50%) were in the failure stage. The level of CK related to AKI varies according to duration of trauma with the highest level was detected on day 2 with value of 3114U/L.

Conclusion: Rhabdomyolysis occurs in up to 85% of patients with traumatic injuries. Patients with severe injuries that develop rhabdomyolysis-induced renal failure have a mortality of approximately 20% but are higher if multiple organ dysfunction is present.

Keywords: Creatine kinase (CK), Renal Failure, Rhabdomyolysis

INTRODUCTION

Rhabdomyolysis is a serious clinical situation. It presents variably from asymptomatic elevation of CK and myoglobin in blood to a life-threatening fulminant AKI^[1].

It is critical to be able to predict rhabdomyolysis-induced AKI. Indeed, 10–50% of patients with marked rhabdomyolysis develop AKI, and it has been suggested that rhabdomyolysis is a cause of 5–25% of all cases of AKI^[1].

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Crush injuries with traumatic rhabdomyolysis are important cause of acute renal failure (ARF). 4% to 33% of cases with traumatic rhabdomyolysis develop ARF, carrying a mortality rate of 3% to 50%^[2].

This study intends to determine the incidence of crush syndrome among polytraumatized patients and level of creatine kinase that is associated with significant renal dysfunction and other complications of crush syndrome such as hyperkalemia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Our study was a prospective cross sectional descriptive study conducted on 50 patients admitted to I.C.U at Al-Helal trauma Centre and Kasr Al-Aini University hospital during the period from October 2015 to August 2016; all the studied populations were diagnosed to have multiple traumas.

In addition, all patients were followed-up for the first three days of admission. We included patients with ISS \geq 16. Patients with chronic kidney disease were excluded from the study.

Data collection included:

I- Demographic data: mainly age and gender.

II- Data used to calculate APACHE II score:

Clinical and laboratory data collected daily in the first three days of ICU stay. These variables include age, Glasgow coma score (GCS), vital signs (temperature, mean arterial pressure, heart rate, respiratory rate), oxygenation variables (FiO₂, PaO₂, arterial pH), chemistry variables (sodium, potassium, creatinine, presence of ARF) and finally hematological variables (hematocrit, total leucocytic count).

III- Injury severity score (ISS):

The ISS score takes values from 0 to 75. Patients with score of 75 (unsurvivable injury) were excluded from our study.

IV- Radiological investigations:

All patients were subjected to radiological investigations as part of trauma survey during the ER stay, including:

A- X-ray: Plain x-ray was done to head, spine, chest, pelvis and limbs.

B- Brain CT: to confirm the presence or absence of intracranial pathology. If CT brain was free and patient still had disturbed consciousness, brain MRI was requested to exclude diffuse axonal injury.

C- Pelvic-abdominal Ultrasound: was performed to all patients in the emergency room or at the bedside in the presence of hemodynamic instability to detect internal hemorrhage and severe abdominal trauma to calculate ISS. Pelvic-abdominal Ultrasound was used to exclude the presence of chronic kidney disease.

VI- Length of stay (LOS) in days:

Date of admission and discharge from ICU were recorded to calculate the LOS in ICU for correlation with the outcome.

VII- Outcome:

All patients were followed up during the ICU stay to determine the primary outcome:

1- Acute kidney injury

Patients who fulfilled RIFLE criteria were diagnosed as AKI and accordingly we divided patients into two groups; group I (GI) includes patients with AKI and group II (GII) includes patients without AKI.

2- Mortality

All ICU mortalities were documented whether related to AKI or not.

The study was approved by the ethical committee of the critical care department, Cairo University.

The current study divided the patients into 2 groups according to development of AKI. Our results showed that group I (GI) included 12 patients versus 38 patients in group II (GII).

Upon analyzing age, there was no significant difference between both groups (mean age 36.08±15.58 vs. 34.89±13.98 years in GI & GII respectively, p-value = 0.804). In addition, there was no significant difference between males and females in relation to AKI (p-value = 0.142).

I. APACHE II score:

When we compared the results of APACHE II scoring system in relation to AKI throughout the follow-up period, we found highly significant difference between both groups as follows (Table 1, Figure 1):

- Day 1: median APACHE II was 14 in GI vs. 6 in GII, p-value = 0.002.
- Day 2: median APACHE II was 13 in GI vs. 4 in GII, p-value <0.001.

Day 3: median APACHE II was 15 in GI vs. 4 in GII, p-value = 0.002.

Table-1: Comparison of APACHE II score between two groups:

APACHE II	GI (n=12)	GII (n=38)	p-value
D1	14	6	0.002
D2	13	4	<0.001
D3	15	4	0.002

Figure-1. Comparison between median APACHE II score and AKI.

II. Injury severity score (ISS):

ISS showed highly significant difference between both groups (mean score 40.33±16.73 in GI vs. 25.34±7.50 in GII, p-value <0.001). (Table 2, Figure 2)

Table-2. Comparison of APACHE II score between two groups:

ISS	GI (n=12)	GII (n=38)
Mean	40.33±16.73	25.34±16.73
Range	17-66	16-43
p-value	<0.001	

RESULTS

Our study included 50 patients with mean age of 35.18±14.22 years old, with male gender constituting 88% of patients (n=44).

Figure-2. Comparison between mean ISS score and AKI.

Figure-4. Incidence of rhabdomyolysis among the two groups

III. Creatine Kinase (CK) level:

When we compared the results of CK levels in relation to AKI throughout the follow-up period we found significant difference between both groups as follows: (Table 3, Figure 3)

- Day 1: 2468.5 U/L in GI vs. 783 U/L in GII, p-value = 0.013.
- Day 2: 4344 U/L in GI vs. 1489 U/L in GII, p-value <0.001.
- Day 3: 3661.5 U/L in GI vs. 733.5U/L in GII, p-value <0.001.

Table-3. Comparison of CK level between two groups:

CK	GI (n=12)	GII (n=38)	p-value
D1 Median (U/L)	2468.5	783	0.013
D2 Median (U/L)	4344	1489	<0.001
D3 Median (U/L)	3661.5	733.5	<0.001

Figure 3: Comparison between CK level and AKI

Further analysis showed highly significant difference between both groups regarding rhabdomyolysis, as all patients (100%) in GI developed rhabdomyolysis compared to 20 patients (52.6%) in GII (p-value = 0.003). (Figure 4).

Further analysis of CK levels to be related to the development of AKI in GI showed the following: (Figure 5).

- Day 1: cutoff point 1385U/L (UAC 0.73, sensitivity 91.7%, and specificity 60.5%).
- Day 2: cutoff point 3114U/L (UAC 0.955, sensitivity 100%, and specificity 89.47%).
- Day 3: cutoff point 1723U/L (UAC 0.9, sensitivity 100%, and specificity 84.21%).

Figure 5: ROC curve showing CK level in relation to AKI.

IV. Length of ICU stay:

Our results showed that AKI has no significant impact on length of ICU stay (median of 5 days in GI vs. 7 days in GII, p-value = 0.655). (Table 4)

Table 4: Comparison of length of ICU stay in both groups:

Length of ICU Stay	GI (n=12)	GII (n=38)	p-value
Median (Days)	5	7	0.655
Range (Days)	4-21	3-25	

V. Outcome:

1. Acute Kidney Injury (AKI):

Our results showed that 12 patients out of 50 (24%) developed AKI. Further analysis showed that 5 patients (41.7%) of them were in risk stage, 1 patient (8.3%) in injury stage and 6 patients (50%) were in failure stage. (Figure 6)

Figure-6: Categorization of patients among the AKI group.

2. Mortality

Our results showed that AKI had a significant impact on mortality where 7 patients (58.3%) died in GI vs. 3 patients (7.9%) in GII, p-value <0.001). (Table 5, Figure 7)

Table 5: Mortality among both groups:

Mortality	GI (n=12)	GII (n=38)	p-value
No.	7	3	
Percentage	58.3%	7.9%	<0.001

Figure-7: Mortality among patient population according to AKI development.

DISCUSSION

Rhabdomyolysis is skeletal muscle destruction with release of intracellular enzymes into the bloodstream. Significant elevation of serum creatine kinase (CK) five to ten folds is characteristic of rhabdomyolysis.

Acute kidney injury (AKI) is the most prevalent systemic complication of rhabdomyolysis, ranging from 10% to 55% and is associated with a poor outcome, particularly in the presence of multiple organ dysfunction.

Therefore, the cornerstone of management is intravenous (IV) fluid therapy so as to preserve the renal function.

Our study was a prospective cross sectional comparative study conducted on 50 patients admitted during the period from October 2015 to August 2016; all the studied populations were diagnosed to have multiple trauma. In addition, all patients were followed-up for the first three days of admission.

The aim of our study is to detect the incidence of rhabdomyolysis among the polytrauma patients, to detect the effect of rhabdomyolysis on developing acute kidney injury (AKI).

We compared between variables in two groups according to the presence or absence of AKI.

Our study revealed that age of our patient population had no significant effect on developing AKI (mean age 36.08±15.58 vs. 34.89±13.98 years in GI & GII respectively, p-value = 0.804). This finding was in concordance with data collected by Sara Ramtinfar et al. 2016 [3] and revealed that there was no significant impact of age on developing AKI (mean age was 36 years in AKI group vs. 32 years in non-AKI group). On the contrary data collected by Mikael Eriksson et al. 2015 [4] revealed highly significant effect of age on developing AKI (median age was 36 years in non-AKI group vs. 54 years in AKI group, p-value = 0.000).

Our patient populations had a highly significant difference between both groups regarding APACHE II score (median APACHE II score 14 in day 1, 13 in day 2 and 15 in day 3 in GI vs. 6 in day 1, 4 in days 2 and 3 in day 3 in GII, p-value = 0.002 in day 1, <0.001 in day 2 and 0.002 in day 3).

Our data were in agreement with Luis Alberto et al. 2015 [5] who found that APACHE II had a significant impact on AKI in ICU (20 for AKI vs. 15 for non-AKI) with a statistically significant difference (p-value = 0.000).

On the contrary, a study performed by Sara Ramtinfar et al. 2016 [3] showed that APACHE II score has no significant effect on AKI (14.9 in AKI group vs. 13.8 in non-AKI group, p-value = 0.317).

Similarly, our study showed highly significant difference between both groups regarding ISS; patients

who developed AKI had higher ISS than those who didn't develop, (40.33 in AKI group vs. 25.34 in non-AKI group, p-value <0.001). Our data were in concordance with data collected by *Mikael Eriksson et al. 2015*^[4] who found that ISS has highly significant impact on AKI (29 in AKI group and 24 in non-AKI group). Also study done by *Wei-Hung Lai 2016*^[6] showed significant impact of ISS on developing AKI (19.2 in AKI group vs. 11.1 in non-AKI group).

On the other hand, *D.L. Skinner et al. 2014*^[7] showed non-significant correlation between AKI and ISS as median ISS was 22 in non-AKI group vs. 25 in AKI group, p-value = 0.665. Similarly, data collected by *John P. et al. 2015*^[8] showed non-significant difference between patients with AKI and patients without AKI regarding ISS (25 in AKI group vs. 22 in non-AKI group, p-value = 0.17).

The current study revealed a significant impact of creatine kinase on developing AKI as patients with AKI had CK levels more than those without AKI (median CK 2468.5 U/L, 4344 U/L and 3661.5 U/L in AKI group vs. 783 U/L, 1489 U/L and 733.5 U/L in non-AKI group for D1, D2 and D3 respectively, p-value 0.013, <0.001 and <0.001). *Arulselvi Subramanian et al. 2013*^[9] showed similar results where higher CK levels was noticed in patients with AKI than those without AKI (median CK 620 U/L, 1360 U/L and 1280.5 U/L in AKI group vs. 287.5 U/L, 636.5 U/L and 416 U/L in non-AKI group for D1, D3 and D5 respectively, p-value 0.00, 0.006 and 0.03).

We also calculated the cutoff values of serum CK for development of AKI on the D1, D2 and D3 by ROC analysis which came out to be ≥ 1385 IU/L, ≥ 3114 IU/L, and ≥ 1723 IU/L, respectively.

The sensitivity in D1 was 91.7% and 100% in D2 and D3. The specificity of serum CK on the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd days was 60.5%, 89.47%, and 84.21% respectively. So, trauma patients with serum CK values above these cutoffs are more liable to develop AKI.

These data were in agreement with data collected by *Arulselvi Subramanian et al. 2013*^[9] revealed cutoff values of serum CK for development of renal failure on the 1st, 3rd, and 5th days by ROC analysis which came out to be ≥ 1320 IU/L, ≥ 1146 IU/L, and ≥ 1754 IU/L, respectively. The sensitivity on the 1st, 3rd, and 5th day was 70%, 55.5%, and 75%, respectively. The specificity of serum CK on the 1st, 3rd, and 5th days was 69%, 55.5%, and 71%, respectively.

The length of ICU stay did not differ significantly according to the development of AKI (median of 5 days in AKI group vs. 7 days in non-AKI group, p-value = 0.655). Our results were in concordance with *Kisoon Ryu et al. 2015*^[10] who revealed non-significant difference between both groups regarding LOS in ICU (9 days in AKI group vs. 8.5 days in non-AKI group, p-value 0.752). Also data collected by *Maria Plataki et al. 2011*^[11] showed non-significant difference between both groups regarding

LOS in ICU as (3 days in AKI group vs. 4 days in non-AKI group, p-value = 0.34).

On the contrary, data collected by *Paulo Roberto Santos 2015*^[12] showed patients with AKI had longer duration of stay in ICU than those without AKI (7.4 days in non-AKI group vs. 9.2 days in AKI group, p-value = 0.021). Also data collected by *John P. Reilly 2015*^[8] showed highly significant impact of AKI on LOS in ICU as (20 days in AKI group vs. 7 days in non-AKI group, p-value 0.001).

Our results showed that AKI had a significant effect on the mortality as 7 patients (58.3%) died in AKI group vs. 3 patients (7.9%) in non-AKI group (p-value <0.001). This finding agreed with data collected by *Paulo Roberto Santo 2015*^[12] who showed that 71.7% of patients in AKI group died vs. only 14.4% of patients in non-AKI group, p-value = 0.000).

CONCLUSION

Patients subjected to severe traumas are liable to develop rhabdomyolysis and subsequent AKI. The serum CL level is considered a good prognostic indicator for renal outcome. Therefore, screening of all multiple trauma patients with biomarkers such as CK is highly recommended.

Conflicts of Interest

Authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper.

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